

A Case Study of Traditional Medical Practitioners living in Khandesh

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Introduction

In Khandesh region, in spite of tribal dominated population in three districts as in Dhule, Jalgaon and Nadurbar, there is hard to find any academic research on the indigenous traditional health practices. The well being of the tribes are ensured by these medicinal practices since ages. The tribal person who is the traditional medical practitioner is called as Vaidhu or Badwa in the region. The 'Vaidhu' is one of the key persons to maintain the status quo of disease free environment in the community. Even today, they rely upon Vaidhu for any minor health related suffering. Thus it is essential to do Vaidhu centric ethnographic, anthropological, participatory qualitative research study. It helped to understand the tribal world of medicine. As the tribal population in the three districts of Khandesh are varies where Bhill tribe is dominated in Nadurbar district. Pawara, Barela and Tadavi tribes are dominated in Jalgaon and Dhule district. The Vaidhu practitioners are predominantly belonging to these tribes.

The tribal traditional medical practice is evident in the Khandesh region. The social, cultural, economic and ecological interest has affected the traditional medical .practices of Vaidhu ,indicator of illness ,practice traditional medicinal ,economic status ,such as social status .therapeutic measurers and vaidhu as a profession ,indicator of health

Social Status

Tribal Vaidhu have the joint families. The family members are averagely 8 to 10 in numbers. Pawara, Tadavi and Bhill communities are having incidentally more number of the practicing Vaidhu. Maximum two children in families are school going. Their income generating profession is agriculture. These Vaidhu are working as farmers or farm labours. They are living in the middle of the village or at the top on the hill. Few of them have rented houses whereas most of them are having their own houses. Housing type is of Kaccha. It is made up of grass, mud and roof is of bricks. Appearance of the Vaidhu is of a modern type wearing pant and shirt. But some of them also wear Hindu religious cloths like a monk. Turban and Dhoti are also used by them. Women are wearing Sarees with ornaments. Exceptionally Vaidhu from Anyardam village of Dhule block was literate and modernised. His house was having structure of cement concrete.

The service oriented professional activity to cure patient called as Vaidhu or Badwa. They have self limiting professional role to cure the individual from sufferings. The heritage of traditional medical practice is passing from old generation. Grand parents are mostly transforming knowledge to new generation. Most of them are the devotee of God/ Goddesses. Worship, fasting and rituals are common. The successful Vaidhu practitioners are giving credit for their knowledge to the blessing of god/ goddesses. The Guru or spiritual people are having the knowledge of traditional medicine, nature and moral values to teach others. In Bhill tribe, Late Shri Sant Aapshri Gulam Maharaj was famous for creating health awareness. He has focused on the community development through his preaching on de-addiction, vegetarian diet, gender equality and respect of other human. Tribal community has accepted this practice for their healthy well being. Vaidhu are socially respected in their community. The individual practitioner has the

support of their family members. They assist not only to collect the medical part of the trees and plants but also to care patients.

Economic Status

The main income source of the Vaidhu is agriculture. They work in farms as labours. They do not have any fix income from the professional practice of Vaidhu. Patients as per their wish are offering money to them. Livestock or animal husbandry is another source of income for these tribal people. Their medical profession is not government recognised. Hence they do not have any benefits of government facilities for professional development. Under the social security schemes of Government tribal people are getting benefits of Gharkul and Public Distribution System across three districts of Khandesh region. But in the few remote villages of tribal community the Government schemes are not functional. Exposure of modern society to tribal society changed their lifestyle in last decade. The continuous decreasing number of Vaidhu practitioners and increasing number of hospitals had an impact on the tribal traditional medical practice.

The BAIF, an NGO, has taken lot of efforts to generate livelihood for Vaidhu in the region. They have trained selected Vaidhu with add on knowledge of naturopathy. Their objectives were to develop professionalise practice of Vaidhu with proper documentation. Unfortunately a sustainable livelihood model could not develop for Vaidhu. The tribal youth are not interested to continue traditional medical practices. The causes are identified such as no fixed income and even basic needs are not satisfied with the practice of it.

Traditional Medical Practice

These Vaidhu are herbalist practitioners. Their practice is to identify, collect and prepare medicine from medicinal part of a plant. It is associated with the rituals of Mantras. Their only objective is well being of the patient from suffering. Traditional medical practice can be learnt by any gender. The worship of god/ goddess and forest is essential along with fasting. The traditional medical knowledge and skills are basic requirements for a good Vaidhu practitioner. The identification of medical plants in forest requires knowledge whereas collections of a particular part in a specific season require good skill.

Concept of health and Illness

'Health is state of wellbeing reflected as happiness'. 'Disease is physical and mental sadness which reflected as pains in hands, legs or cramps and headache etc'. 'Pain in a particular organ is also called a disease'. The origin of disease is contaminated food, water and environment. Mainly patients are suffering with fever, body ache, headache, cramps, Kavil i.e. Yellowish eyes (hepatitis), Lakhwa (Paralysis), Mutkhada (renal stone) and vaginal white discharge of a woman. Their idea of origin of disease is like continuous fever will persist as the yellowish eyes. Hence fever is origin of the Kavil disease. Every Vaidhu has specific ideas about the origin, progress and cure of disease. The confirmation of patient's cure is observed in the follow up visits only. The environmental changes are the basic causes of the disease. Seasonal changes have the significant impact on the diagnosis of disease. Cultural practices of eating and drinking are also the causes of the disease conditions. The festive seasons or celebrations as in Holi, Diwali, Navami and Navratri have incidences to increase morbidity rate. The common cause of morbidity is alcohol drinking.

Therapeutic Measures

Vaidhu have few symptomatic remedial preparations which are enlisted. (Please refer Annexure) The Nadi Parikshan, Bunch of Neem Leaves or flour of Jwar are used in the diagnosis of the illness. Vaidhu are using different methods to diagnosis like Keeping

Jwar seeds near legs of patient or by moving water or maize flour above the head of a patient or keeping hand on the stomach or on any painful organ etc. Sometimes they are using astrology. The rituals are completed in few sittings at temple with Mantras. Vaidhu in Nadurbar district are using tribal songs associated with Mantras for betterment of patient. A lady Vaidhu told that she used a coin of one rupee to diagnose a disease. She also asked patient to bath at special place "Manosar". Use of mantras and special threads of blessings are used by her. Predominantly medicines are given to patients with sufferings of body ache, headache, sprain and cramps etc. As soon as the patient feels better they offer coconut, non veg food, sweets or snacks etc. To Vaidhu. As per the demand of Vaidhu, sometimes alcohol is also offered by patients.

Preventive Measures

Medical healers have given significant importance to preventive measures. They always asked to keep cleanliness of environment with good hygienic habits and nutritious food. Self care is vital for everyone. That helps to be healthy body, mind and spirit. Vaidhu have strong assumption that environment and human being have strong relationship. Change in the environment affects the health of the individual. It is the origin of illness. Pleasant, clean and peaceful environment keep human being healthy.

Vaidhu Profession

Vaidhu's practice is mostly effective in village level or block level. Professional limitations and challenges are diverse as change in the locality and geographical positioning of the tribes. Local community people or tribal society has a respect for this traditional medical practice. It is essential qualities of a Vaidhu i.e. To have dedication, self determination and traditional medical knowledge of generations. Some of them believe that the traditional rituals should be practiced by every Vaidhu. The worship and fasting to praise God and Goddess and forest should be regular. It is mandatory in the festive seasons like Navami, Navratri and Holi. Vaidhu profession is dependent on the medical plants of forests. But destruction of forest worried the Vaidhu. Hence worship of nature and preservation medical plants in the forests are significant.

Conclusion:

The present study is exploring the tribal world of traditional medical practice in Khandesh region. Vaidhu are doing traditional medical practice but quantitative and qualitative practices are decreasing. More close association of tribal villagers to modern society enforced tribes to imbibe modern culture. The conceptual idea of tribes about illness is socially dysfunctional due to specific signs and symptoms. Their modus operandi of medical practice is based on the knowledge grand parents, pleasant environment and belief on the supernatural powers. The cleanliness and hygienic behaviour is specially focused in their practice. Most of the Vaidhu are illiterate or educated up to IV standard. Superstitious practices and alcoholic behaviours are commonly seen across all tribal villages. Their cultural identity is at stake where rapid growth of cities is engulfing tribal villages and resources.

The natural resources like forest and rivers are alienated to tribes. Hence they are in phase to loss their own identity. The remote tribes in the Nadurbar districts are still practicing their traditional practices. As earlier researches had argued, the cultural based health care system is a need of tribes. The tribal youth are getting benefits of various Government schemes for education. That helped them to look for various career avenues. These tribal youth are also taking modern medical education. They are M.B.B.S. and B.A.M.S. degree holders. Their hospitals are situated at block level whereas they are serving to their tribal communities. The numbers are still two or three but trends are changing in traditional medical practices. In the globalisation tribal culture is modernised where the indigenous

symbols are changed to the religious identity. The worship pattern, clothing pattern, ceremonial celebrations and photos of the religious guru eventually transformed their tribal cultural identity into a modern religious culture. Ultimately the preservation of these practices is essential as cultural identity and heritage of tribes.

Recommendations

1. Community health programs especially activities of Department of AYUSH should develop the collaborative efforts to empower tribal Vaidhu.
2. Professional Social Workers should plan their field activities in the tribal villages to document tribal traditional practices.
3. The Vaidhu are the primary health workers in village. They can be used as the primary resource of community care for tribes.
4. The folk dances, skits and street plays should be made popular to aware about the health education.
5. Education facilities should reach to every one and primary care should be the compulsory part of their education.
6. Cultural sacred practices such as worship of nature, forest and deities should be the part of their local health programs.
7. The special training clinics should be planned for Vaidhu to become primary accredited health worker.
8. The facilities and government schemes should be planned to cultivate medicinal plants and kitchen gardens in the region.
9. Cured cases of Vaidhu should be highlighted and referred for the training of others.
10. Cultural beliefs of tribes should be understood and the health programs should be designed in framework of tribal culture.
11. Educated youth should motivate others to respect tribal culture and promote traditional medical practice.
12. The role of Government is pioneering to preserve and promote the tribe's culture. The project cycle should be designed immediately to strengthen tribal traditional medical practices.

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